

ISic2761

I.Sicily inscription 2761

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

prayer

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Hybla Heraea

Place of origin (modern)

Ragusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Ragusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329962

1. [— — —] ²3(?) rhombi² ΦΕ [— —]
2. [— — — —] ΜΕΘΕΞ (?) ἔξελεθ (ε) διάβο-
3. λε
4. ²4 rhombi² Ἄδωνα [ι] ²3 rhombi²
5. ²6 rhombi² Ε.Ι Σα-
6. βαὼθ ΑΡΑΚΙΑ
7. ²2 rhombi² [— — — —]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285164

EDCS 64600458

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 18.0415

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1953. Epigrafi magiche cristiane della Sicilia orientale. *Rendiconti delle sedute dell'Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Classe di Scienze morali, storiche e filologiche*. ser.VIII vol.8: 181-189. At 183-184 ph

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